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Synthesis of Steroidal Extranucleo Thiazolidones of Cholestane Series

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THIAZOLIDONES have been found to be endowed with a variety of biological activities¹. The ketones, 6-oxo-5 α -cholestan-3 β -yl acetate² (1a) and 3-oxo-5-cholestene³ (2a) were reacted with hydrazine hydrate in alcoholic solution to obtain the corresponding hydrazones (1b, 2b); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 300, 3 200 (NH₂) and 1 425, 1 415 cm⁻¹ (C=N). The compound (1b, 2b) when refluxed with ammonium thiocyanate in benzene solution gave the respective thiosemicarbazones (1c, 2c); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 300, 3 150 (NH₂) and 1 125 cm⁻¹ (C=S).

1a; X=O
1b; X=NNH₂
1c; X=NNHOSNH₂

2a; X=O
2b; X=NNH₂
2c; X=NNHOSNH₂

3a

3b

4a

4b

The cyclisation of (1c, 2c) with chloroacetic acid in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate and acetic acid furnished 6-diazo-5 α -cholestan-6-(1',3'-thiazolidan-4'-one)-3 β -yl acetate (3a) and 3-diazo-5-cholesten-3-(1',3'-thiazolidan-4'-one) (4a), respectively; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 300 (NH), 1 715 (C=O of thiazolidone) and 1 425, 1 415 cm⁻¹ (C=C, C=N); δ 7.8 (1H, s, NH, disappeared on addition of D₂O) and 5.4 (2H, s, CH₂ of thiazolidone); ¹³C nmr δ 220 (C=O of thiazolidone), 160 (C=N) and 73 (CH₂ of thiazolidone). The alternate structures (3b, 4b) are precluded on the basis of ¹³C nmr spectra as they are expected to show the signal for CH₂ of thiazolidone at δ 90.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer, PMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A60 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and the ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a JEOL JNN FX-100 (25.00 Mz) spectrometer (temp., 25°) using TMS as internal standard.

Hydrazones (1b, 2b): The ketone (1a, 2a; 1.75 g) was refluxed with freshly distilled hydrazine hydrate (1 ml) in ethanolic (35 ml) in the presence of acetic acid (1 drop) for 2 h. The excess solvent was then distilled off and the residual solution was poured into ice-cold water. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried, and recrystallised from ethanol (1b, 2b; 1.55 g) (Table 1).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Analysis %: Found/(Calcd.)		
			O	H	N
1b	147	C ₂₈ H ₅₀ N ₂ O ₂	76.02 (75.98)	10.98 (10.91)	6.23 (6.11)
2b	158-59	C ₂₇ H ₄₈ N ₂	81.56 (81.61)	11.85 (11.83)	7.16 (7.05)
1c	120-22	C ₂₈ H ₅₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	65.89 (65.81)	9.25 (9.32)	7.53 (7.67)
2c	190-92	C ₂₇ H ₄₉ N ₃ S	73.78 (73.68)	10.06 (10.08)	9.27 (9.20)
3a	104-06	C ₃₃ H ₅₄ N ₂ O ₄ S	68.75 (68.94)	9.23 (9.15)	7.52 (7.54)
4a	134-36	C ₃₀ H ₄₈ N ₂ OS	72.67 (72.58)	9.23 (9.27)	8.52 (8.46)

Thiosemicarbazones (1c, 2c): To the compound (1b, 2b; 2 g) in benzene (100 ml) was added ammonium thiocyanate (2 g), and the reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The excess benzene was then distilled off and the concentrated solution cooled and the resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from alcohol to yield the product (1c, 2c; 1.65 g) (Table 1).

Thiazolidone (3a, 4a): The thiosemicarbazone (1c, 2c; 1 g) was refluxed with chloroacetic acid (0.3 g) in presence of sodium acetate (0.4 g) and acetic acid (30 ml) for 6-8 h. The excess solvent

was then distilled off under reduced pressure and the concentrated solution was poured into ice cold water. The resulting solid was filtered, washed, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to yield the product (3a, 4a ; 0.75 g) which gave a single spot on tlc in benzene - acetone system (Table 1).

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Nitromethane Synthesis with D-Ribose

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FISCHER and Sowden¹ performed experiments in the stepping up of aldoses. Aldoses were condensed with nitromethane in presence of sodium methoxide to form the corresponding nitroalcohols which were then subjected to the Nef reaction² with moderately concentrated sulphuric acid to form the higher aldose.

Here D-ribose has been condensed with nitromethane in presence of sodium methoxide to form 1-nitro-1-deoxy-D-altritol (1) and 1-nitro-1-deoxy-D-allitol (2). To this mixture some pyridine was then added and the products were separated in a small centrifuge. While 1 dissolved in pyridine, the latter did not. Then 1 was subjected to the Nef reaction

with 7 N H₂SO₄ to form D-altrose (3) and with 2 N H₂SO₄ to form D-allose (4).

Experimental

Condensation of D-ribose with nitromethane: A suspension of D-ribose (2.5 g) in methanol (8 ml) and nitromethane (7 ml) was shaken with a solution of sodium (2.3 g) in methanol (6 ml) and then allowed to stand in an ice-box for 1.5 h when the sodium salts of the sugar nitroalcohols precipitated. The precipitate was filtered, washed with cold ethanol and then with ether. To it pyridine (7.5 ml) was added and the mixture was separated by centrifugation. The epimer 1 dissolved in pyridine while 2 did not. Pyridine was distilled off to obtain 1 (1.8 g), m.p. 68° (Found: C, 34.10; H, 6.09; N, 6.60. Calcd.: C, 34.12; H, 6.11; N, 6.63%); [α]_D -4.2° (H₂O). From the undissolved portion, 2 was obtained (0.2 g), m.p. 46° (Found: C, 34.11; H, 6.10; N, 6.61. Calcd.: C, 34.12; H, 6.11; N, 6.63%); [α]_D +1.2° (H₂O).

Nef reaction of 1 and 2: 1 (1.8 g) was warmed with 7 N H₂SO₄ (4 ml) for 1 h. The excess acid was then removed on an ion-exchange column. From the filtrate D-altrose (3; 1.2 g) crystallised out, m.p. 104°; [α]_D -24° (H₂O); it formed a benzylphenyl-